

**3-D STRESS DISTRIBUTION:
A FINITE ELEMENT APPROACH**

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ABSTRACT

In this paper a three-dimensional method for determining stresses or strains in laminated plates is presented. The governing equations of the system are obtained using the principle of stationary complementary energy and they are divided into two differential systems whereby the variables are partly separated. The solution is obtained using an iterative procedure. A few results are presented.

INTRODUCTION

The problems of laminated plates under in-plane loading can be solved by classical theory of elasticity under the assumption of plane stress or plane strain by substituting the laminated plate by a homogeneous plate having the gross properties of the laminate. Analyses of laminated plates by this procedure are in general inadequate, especially for laminated composites, since they do not take factors into account which have significant influence on the mechanical response of the laminates. These are factors such as stacking sequence and interlaminar normal and shear stresses. The significance of the mentioned factors in the analyses of composite laminates is well documented by some numerical investigations, Pipes and Pagano (1) and Wang and Crossman (2), and by some experimental investigations, Daniels et al. (3).

Consequently, three-dimensional theories are needed in the analyses of laminated plates under in-plane loading in order to get a proper understanding and description of their me-

chanical response. Three-dimensional analyses of laminates create difficulties and they often become too complex. Often, numerical methods such as FEM have to be consulted in order to be successful in the analyses of laminates. However, the analysis of laminates by numerical methods demands enormous computer storage capacity to get a proper description of the response of the laminate through the thickness. Furthermore, realistic numerical investigations of the laminates become technically difficult and economically irresponsible as the number of layers becomes even moderately large.

In this paper a new (quasi) three-dimensional theory for orthotropic laminated plates under in-plane loading will be presented, which ultimately leads to a finite element approach. The great advantage of this new finite element approach is that it gives a full three-dimensional description of the stresses (or strains) within the whole laminate without needing enormous computer storage capacity as for traditional FEM approaches. This is due to the fact that the variation of the stress field through the thickness of a laminate is solved partly independently of the in-plane variation.

The development of the three-dimensional theory follows the approach of ref. (4), but differs significantly, since a new stress field description is adopted and laminates of orthotropic layers are considered.

The governing equations for the layered plate are obtained by applying the variational principle of stationary complementary potential energy to an assumed form of the stress field. The assumed stress field will satisfy the equilibrium equations of the three-dimensional elasticity and the boundary conditions. The theory is approximate since the compatibility or continuity conditions are satisfied only in an average sense. The purpose of this paper is to give a description of the fundamental theory behind the approach. However, some results for different lay up angles are presented at the end of the paper.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Consider a laminated plate of the thickness $2h$ consisting of m laminae with each lamina having individual thicknesses and material properties, see figure 1.

Let $\sigma_1^{(p)}(x_1, x_2, x_3)$ be the stress distribution in the p^{th} lamina. (x_1, x_2, x_3) is a fixed cartesian coordinate system with the plane $x_3 = 0$ coinciding with the middle plane of the plate. In order to simplify the analysis it will be assumed that the plate is symmetric with respect to the middle plane ($x_3 = 0$).

Without loss of generality the stress distribution in the p^{th} layer is divided into two parts, one which is only a function of the in-plane coordinates x_1 and x_2 , and one which is a function of both the coordinates x_1 and x_2 , and the out-of-plane (transverse) coordinate x_3 :

$$\sigma_1^{(p)}(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \tilde{S}_1(x_1, x_2) + \bar{\sigma}_1^{(p)}(x_1, x_2, x_3) \quad (1)$$

where $i = 1 \dots 6$ and $p = 1 \dots m$.

The major assumption in this analysis is connected with the stress distribution part $\bar{\sigma}_1^{(p)}$:

Figure 1. Multi-layered plate

'Assume the stress distribution part $\bar{\sigma}_i^{(p)}$ to be a product of two functions, one giving the variance of $\bar{\sigma}_i^{(p)}$ through the thickness and one giving the in-plane variance'. That is:

$$\sigma_i^{(p)}(x_1, x_2, x_3) = \tilde{S}_i(x_1, x_2) + S_i(x_1, x_2) f_i^{(p)}(x_3) \quad (2)$$

The second restriction on the stress field is that the equilibrium conditions (neglecting the body forces) are to be fulfilled independently of the functions $f_i^{(p)}(x_3)$. Letting $f_3^{(p)}(x_3) = f_p(x_3)$ this restriction leads to

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_1^{(p)} &= \tilde{S}_1 + S_1 \cdot f_p''(x_3) \\ \sigma_2^{(p)} &= \tilde{S}_2 + S_2 \cdot f_p''(x_3) \\ \sigma_3^{(p)} &= \tilde{S}_3 + S_3 \cdot f_p'(x_3) \\ \sigma_4^{(p)} &= \tilde{S}_4 - S_4 \cdot f_p'(x_3) \\ \sigma_5^{(p)} &= \tilde{S}_5 - S_5 \cdot f_p'(x_3) \\ \sigma_6^{(p)} &= \tilde{S}_6 + S_6 \cdot f_p''(x_3) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The equilibrium equations are now given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{S}_{1,1} + \tilde{S}_{6,2} &= 0 \\
 \tilde{S}_{6,1} + \tilde{S}_{2,2} &= 0 \\
 S_{1,1} + S_{6,2} - S_5 &= 0 \\
 S_{6,1} + S_{2,2} - S_4 &= 0 \\
 S_{5,1} + S_{4,2} - S_3 &= 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

The upper and lower surfaces of the plate are assumed to be free of traction, therefore:

$$f_1(-h) = f'_1(-h) = f_m(h) = f'_m(h) = 0 \tag{5}$$

Furthermore, this restriction yields:

$$\tilde{S}_3 = \tilde{S}_4 = \tilde{S}_5 = 0 \tag{6}$$

The governing equations for the stress distribution are obtained by using a variational method. The total complementary energy π^* of the whole laminate is the sum of the contribution from each lamina:

$$\pi^* = \sum_{p=1}^m \left\{ \int_{V_p} W_p^* dV - \int_{\Gamma_u} \sum_{i=1}^3 T_i^{(p)} U_i^{(p)} d\Gamma \right\} \tag{7}$$

W_p^* is the complementary strain energy density of the p^{th} lamina and is defined as follows for linear elastic materials:

$$W_p^* = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^6 \sigma_i^{(p)} \epsilon_i^{(p)} \tag{8}$$

where the $\sigma_i^{(p)}$'s are given by eq. (3) with the restrictions of eq. (6) and the $\epsilon_i^{(p)}$'s are given according to the normal constitutive equation for orthotropic materials.

$T_i^{(p)}$ and $W_i^{(p)}$ are the tractions and the displacements, respectively, prescribed over the edge boundary $\Gamma_u^{(p)}$ where $\Gamma^{(p)}$ is the lateral edge boundary of the p^{th} lamina. The stress distribution in eq. (8) and thereby in eq. (7) must fulfil the equilibrium equations given by eq. (4). This constraint is incorporated in the functional by means of Lagrangian multipliers. The new functional is then:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{\pi}^* &= \pi^* - \int_A \{ \tilde{\lambda}_1 (\tilde{S}_{1,1} + \tilde{S}_{6,2}) + \tilde{\lambda}_2 (\tilde{S}_{6,1} + \tilde{S}_{2,2}) + \lambda_1 (S_{1,1} + S_{6,2} - S_5) \\
 &+ \lambda_2 (S_{6,1} + S_{2,2} - S_4) + \lambda_3 (S_{5,1} + S_{4,2} - S_3) \} dx_1 dx_2
 \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

where A denotes the total area of the middle plane.

The principle of stationary complementary potential energy states:

'Of all possible equilibrium stress fields for a laminate subjected to prescribed loading and boundary displacements, the true equilibrium one corresponding to a compatible displacements field renders the functional $\bar{\pi}^$ a stationary value'.*

The principle leads to the governing equations for the functions $f_p, \tilde{S}_1, \tilde{S}_2, \tilde{S}_6, S_1, S_2, S_3, S_4, S_5, S_6, \tilde{\lambda}_1, \tilde{\lambda}_2, \lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3$ which are obtained by:

$$\delta \bar{\pi}^* = 0 \tag{10}$$

The governing equation for f_p becomes

$$H_1^{(p)} f_p^{(IV)}(x_3) + (2H_3^{(p)} - H_2^{(p)}) f_p''(x_3) + H_6^{(p)} f_p(x_3) = J_2^{(p)'}(x_3) - J_1^{(p)''}(x_3) - \dot{H}_6^{(p)} \tag{11}$$

and f_p must fulfil certain boundary and continuity conditions (not presented in this paper). The H-functions are integrals of the form:

$$\int_A A_{ij}^{(p)} R_i R_j dA \quad (\text{no summation})$$

where $A_{ij}^{(p)}$ are the coefficients of the compliance matrix for the p^{th} layer, and R_i are the functions \tilde{S}_i or S_i . The J-functions are related to the external work as H is related to the internal work.

The governing equations for the functions $\tilde{S}, S, \tilde{\lambda}$ and λ are

$$[I] = \begin{Bmatrix} S_1 \\ S_2 \\ S_3 \\ S_4 \\ S_5 \\ S_6 \\ \tilde{S}_1 \\ \tilde{S}_2 \\ \tilde{S}_6 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} -\lambda_{1,1} \\ -\lambda_{2,2} \\ -\lambda_3 \\ -\lambda_{3,2} \quad -\lambda_2 \\ -\lambda_{3,1} \quad -\lambda_1 \\ -\lambda_{1,2} \quad -\lambda_{2,1} \\ -\tilde{\lambda}_{1,1} \\ -\tilde{\lambda}_{2,2} \\ -\tilde{\lambda}_{1,2} \quad -\tilde{\lambda}_{2,1} \end{Bmatrix} \tag{12}$$

The coefficients of the 9x9 matrix [I] can be interpreted as weighted average compliance coefficients, and they are given through eq. (10). The boundary conditions can either be expressed in terms of \tilde{S} and S (i.e. tractions) or in terms of $\tilde{\lambda}$ and λ (i.e. displacements).

If the matrix [I] is non-singular, as it should be since it represents the compliance of the plate (it should also be positive definite), eq. (12) can be rewritten:

$$\{S\} = [I]^{-1} \{\lambda^g\} \tag{13}$$

Here the symbols $\{S\}, \{\lambda^g\}$ have been substituted for the vectors in eq. (12).

Substituting eq. (13) into eq. (14) and solving for $\tilde{\lambda}$ and λ a differential system for determining $\tilde{\lambda}_1, \tilde{\lambda}_2, \lambda_1, \lambda_2$ and λ_3 is obtained:

$$[D]\{\lambda\} = \{0\} \quad (14)$$

The vector $\{\lambda\}$ contains the functions $\tilde{\lambda}_1, \tilde{\lambda}_2, \lambda_1, \lambda_2$ and λ_3 and the 5×5 matrix $[D]$ contains up to second order differential operators.

Eq. (11) and eq. (14) together with the corresponding boundary and continuity conditions give the governing equations for the determination of the stress distribution. Eq. (11) is a fourth order linear inhomogeneous differential equation which can be solved using Laplace transformation. Eq. (14) is solved using a finite element approach. A triangular six-node element with quadratic shape functions is used and a linear set of equations is accomplished using the Galerkin method. The resulting stress distribution is now given by eq. (2) and eq. (6).

The procedure in the approach is now, given the material constants, the geometry and the boundary conditions for the plate solve eq. (11) and eq. (14) to get the stresses given by eq. (3). Since the coefficients in eq. (11) depend on the in-plane distribution and the coefficients in eq. (14) depend on the transverse distribution these equations must be solved in an iterative way. The problem herein is to get a good approximation for either the matrix $[I]$ of eq. (12) or the functions f_p governed by eq. (11). At the present time it seems that the most promising method is to get an approximation for the f_p functions.

Denoting by C_{11}^p the compliance coefficient for the p th layer combining $\sigma_1^{(p)}$ and $\epsilon_1^{(p)}$, and by $\langle C_{11} \rangle$ the average compliance matrix of the whole plate. It is simple to show by some small approximations that

$$f_p'' = (C_{11}^p - \langle C_{11} \rangle) / \langle C_{11} \rangle \quad (15)$$

Eq. (15) suggests that a good approximation is obtained by assuming a transverse distribution described in terms of cosine and sine functions fulfilling eq. (15) in the middle of each lamina. Using this approximation as an input for the iterative process the $[I]$ matrix converges for most laminates in less than 30 iterations. The relative divergence of the coefficients of the $[I]$ matrix is after approximately 30 iterations less than .05 per cent.

RESULTS

Although the computer programming of the present method is not yet fully developed a few results are presented in this paper. As mentioned it is important to get a proper approximation for the transverse distribution f_p . The method in connection with eq. (15) gives the f -distribution shown in figure 2. Note that the function has been normalized with respect to the value at the middle plane of the plate. The vertical lines symbolize the lamina interfaces.

The moduli in the planes of symmetry of each layer are:

$$\begin{aligned} E_{11} &= 59\,000 \text{ MPa} & E_{22} &= E_{33} = 24\,000 \text{ MPa} \\ G_{23} &= 12\,000 \text{ MPa} & G_{12} &= G_{13} = 9\,000 \text{ MPa} \\ \nu_{23} &= 0.02 & \nu_{12} &= \nu_{13} = 0.27 \end{aligned}$$

where the subscripts 1, 2 and 3 refer to the fibre, transverse and thickness directions, respectively. The material considered is a glass/epoxy lamina (Fibredux 914G - R - 7 - 32) (5).

Figure 2. F-function for the lay-up angles $[90, 0, 45, -45]_3$. Thickness $2h = 1.0$ mm.

Figure 3. Convergence of f -function. (The plate is loaded by extension in the x_2 -direction).

For the laminate concerned the f function was acceptable after 50 iterations. Figure 3 shows the f functions for some of the iterations. Note again that the functions have been normalized.

CONCLUSION

A three-dimensional theory for the determination of stresses and strains in laminated composite plates has been established. The governing equations are simplified to two differential systems, one solvable by Laplace transformations and one by a FEM approach.

It is shown that a rough approximation of the transverse stress distribution leads to an acceptable solution within 30 - 50 iterations dependent on the choice of lay-up angles.

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